

Session 8 live-captioning, Friday, 23 June 2023:

[Cosmology and large scale surveys](#)

Ami Choi: Weak lensing with JWST and Roman, current insights and future synergies

Hi, everyone. We are the last but not least session of our conference, cosmology in large-scale survey. Very excited to have Ami Choi telling us about weak lensing with JWST and Roman.

Ami: Thanks. And thanks to the organizers and also other speakers and attendees. I've been learning a lot and it makes me really excited to see the continuing emerging results from JWST and thinking about how we will use them in conjunction with Roman data and also use them are prepared for Roman period my talk will be a little bit different from most of the other talks so far in the sense that as you will see, we lensing is really a statistical measurement. There are actually aren't that many we lensing results yet from JWST although there is at least one.

Maybe those of you in the audience when people tell me if I've missed something. All right, this is a quick look at my talk. I'll start by talking about weak lensing and motivating why we want to use it to explore the universe. I'll also talk about what the current results are, what we are seeing with today's surveys and then I'll talk about how we are preparing for measurements with Nancy Grace Roman space telescope and I'll talk about the road ahead. And then you'll see all of these things. Just can skip through that. This is our picture of the universe. It can have the obligatory timeline universe in a nutshell plot so we are starting over here on the left and is the universe, galaxies and objects, stars and objects for mangle and form into galaxies and then we have more structure forming and then we are here on the right-hand side. Every galaxy surveys, at least from the ground are mostly telling us about the late time universe. These are structures that formed in the last 5 to 10000000000 years and we also have information from the cosmic microwave background which is telling us about the early time universe. That's one of the snapshots of the universe and it's really, really infant stages. Of course, with JWST where we are revealing a lot of the first astronomical objects in this middle region here, and a Roman will also explore that region too. It will really explain that we are learning about the late time universe now much further to the left ear. The overall question that I've been interested in trying to answer in the last many years is generally described the universe, the physics of the universe with a single model that is comprised of dark matter and dark energy and also with a set of six parameters which are the same across the entire 13 billion -- over 13 billion years. So, here is a simulation of the elementary structure of the universe and in these peaks, density peaks, we

can see galaxies. They are tracing that structure. What we want to learn about is the matter and we found out from multiple observations that the matter is mostly dark matter. We can't really see it directly. It turns out that -- here's another simulation where we see the story. When we see the dark matter and in these blue... Here are meant to illustrate galaxies and we can see the galaxies are aligned with the star better structure. That's already how we can learn about that underlying structures. Lensing is the particular phenomenon that causes those galaxies to be aligned with the foreground large-scale structure. It's a really subtle effect we think about weak gravitational dancing so a lot of you are probably familiar with strong gravitational lens and where we can actually see with our eyes the impact on the images of the galaxies. Really highly distorted, might be multiple images and so forth. With weak lensing, it can be something like 0.1 impact on the electricity of the galaxy shapes and lensing is specifically sensitive to the mass density of the universe. Although the amplitude fluctuations. This little Sigma H is also combined with this Mega M or the mass density into a parameter called SH which is kind of like some amplitude of the structure fluctuations. This is a schematic of lensing. On the left ear. Thanks to Pat's talk yesterday, is a diagram of diffraction angles and this is really very much like that, but showing us the distant galaxies with the light coming towards us. But we are seeing is this projected 2D image here. These galaxies which were in this illustration originally round, as they go past some heavy objects, could be heavy galaxies, groups of galaxies, clusters of galaxies, those objects are playing down the space-time. So what we actually see is our images were the path of the light traveling from those really distant galaxies have been distorted. These galaxies images appear as being stretched. For this case, it's stretched along the line of sight relative to the center of where these foreground structures are. The two important ingredients of weak gravitational dancing are shown here. We need to make good measurements of the source galaxy shapes and we also need some understanding of the redshift distributions along the line of sight oath to the objects that are doing the lensing in the very background galaxies by the light is traveling from. The shapes of Paquin galaxies are aligned with the foreground structure. Cosmic shear that specifically a shorthand term for lensing by a logical structure. This is usually measured as some sort of correlations of galaxy shapes as a function of separation in the sky. There is some -- we are trying to look for coherent patterns. These are both aligned in some way. Pairs of galaxies as a function of redshift. Then galaxies of the trace the underlying battlefield, modulo, some quantity called Galaxy bias. There is too additional correlations we can look at. Previously, I talked about the sheep-shaped correlations and we can also correlate positions of galaxies. This is telling us about galaxy clustering. As a function of separation. Finally, we can correlate the positions of foreground galaxies with background galaxy shapes. This is known as galaxy-galaxy lensing for shorthand. Now we can think about all the galaxy surveys that have been designed for cosmic shear. At the end, I'll talk about some of the results that are not on the main part of the plot. Starting with the first detection of cosmic shear in 2,000. It was over 20 years ago. There were several surveys. Sort of in the mid-2000s passed that going well into the 20 tens. Then, we are -- okay. Here with the. That still happening now so stay tuned. That's the last stop at least from the ground-based perspective. Up until we get Euclid which is launching in a matter of weeks. It's about two weeks from now. It's going to lunch. And also the Vera Rubin. I think it's going to start in 2025. That will run for ten years. Of course Roman, as you've heard, will launch somewhere between October 2026 and May of 2027. That will have a nominal five year mission that we are hoping that it will last for at least

10. I said I'd mention a little bit about SDSS and HST. SDSS ground-based very large portion of the sky. Kind of shallow and clearly not designed for lensing in terms of the image resolution. But did still produce very important resource for cosmic shear. Also, there were some HST service. I think the first one was a gem survey in 2005 and then as you probably are familiar with, because must also had a number of important cosmic shear results. These are also precursors to what JWST will show us with cosmos web so that's something I was super excited to hear from about yesterday. I'm looking forward to for the results there. The last thing I'll mention here is that the size of the teams have really been growing as the error bar decreases. This is something that we need to think about in terms of how we operate together these large collaborations. Going into the current landscape, I'm not going to go into too much detail here because it there's quite a lot. I did want to give you an overview of how do we go from the images to actually getting these funny looking contour plots at the end here, some of which -- this one is not a banana but some of you might be familiar with this comment banana shape we have the matter density on the x-axis and then the little Σ_8 on the Y-axis. This is classic degeneracy that is irrigated along this direction. Since this is a combine parameter, it looks a little bit different. there is quite a lot going into these. There's a lot of processing that goes on even in between some of the steps that I have here. Just to highlight some of the very important steps are to correct -- to accurately characterize the point spread function to measure galaxy shapes to figure out your redshift distributions and calibrate them. You'll probably want to do a lot of simulations when you're testing your algorithms for shape measurement. Testing what happens when your objects are blended, what kind of systematic that impart your analysis. Then you're making measurements of some of those correlation functions that I mentioned earlier. And then there is a huge effort also going into modeling and analysis. That part is also -- I would say each of these kind of a different chunks. I've delineated that here. It's just very large, hardworking teams over many years that create the results for each of these. I'll talk a little bit more about the modeling and analysis choices for recent work that we just finished. At the very end of it, you run a sampling of the likelihood and you get some sort of parameter plot that looks like this. Another thing I'll mention is that we've been trying to mitigate experiment bias or what people commonly call blinding where there are different levels of running or observation that we are trying to make sure that we know what other large-scale structure surveys found. We don't want to unintentionally make choices that lead to exactly that same answer. There is some players here when we try to make sure that we can at least try to mitigate that experimenter bias. I talk about briefly about one of the very recent results that we just wrapped up several weeks ago. But point -- this is a collaboration between two of the cosmic shear surface that I mentioned earlier. I'm a member of both the Alex Amon is a member of both. I would say the actual team that was necessary to produce this result is really huge. It doesn't even -- it goes beyond the names that are on this plot are on the slide. These were the main contributors. We wanted to see what happens when you combine the latest results from the KiDS survey and in the dark energy survey. The most recent results. Some brief thoughts about where the surveys are in the sky. This blue outline here, it's been referred to either as a tank or a hummingbird depending on what you want to see there. There is also the killer degreaser and I should also point out this Y3. That means the observations taken through the first three years of observations. There is actually six years of observations in total which are being analyzed and happy at the kilo-degree survey is comprised of these two orange chunks here. And then, the

latest data set is called 1,000 because it's about 1,000 square degrees. The hyper-suprime camera survey which in our paper we don't compare that, for the reason that as you can see here, the footprint except for the small figures appear, they are very much overlapping both DES and KiDS so there is a very complicated covariance matrix that we would need to fully understand which that would be published in medical project or something like that. To understand the correlation between and the cross covariance between these different datasets. We do -- we did work with the HSC team to produce some results using a pipeline that we developed and applying it to their most recent results. Here are some stats. They are really complementary. DES is the largest but it has the smallest number density of source galaxies and then KiDS also has the benefit of multiple bands, like filters. It goes out to near infrared so it has better, more accurate photometric redshift spirit friendly, HSC just has a really amazing seeing and so the number density is really great and it's terrific for lensing. Although on the other hand, it is much smaller field. I'm just going to show you the results and not go into too much detail. What we did was combine DES why three in kids are so the spec contour here and in the original KiDS and DES results are here with one caveat which is that we devised a particular type in which we call the hybrid pipeline, choosing between different analysis choices that the different surveys conducted for the published results. There is a little bit of difference from the actual published results will differ KiDS and DES here because these are the results using a hybrid pipeline. We did a huge market analysis testing out different choices affected the end result on a simulated data affected. We would be looking at how things like changing our intrinsic alignments model which is one particular systematic for lensing since we are assuming with lensing that all the objects in the sky that we are using are oriented randomly but actually is, there is galaxy and they behave relative to one another in ways that causes some sort of gravitational tidal forces when they are actually become oriented in a particular way. There are many other things that we were considering. The bottom line here is that when we run our hybrid pipeline on the combined DES why three in KiDS 1,000 data vector, we get a 2% precision on this estate parameter and it's less intelligent with Planck than KiDS was by itself and more than DES was by itself. It's closer to 2 Sigma so we have seen a lot of recent large-scale structure lensing surveys, but this 2 Sigma difference from Planck and that's one of the main reasons we were interested in looking at the combined statistical power of our measurement. That was the Takeaway. I think I said this already, so 2% precision on S8 and the model seems to fit very well. This is what it looks like in one dimension and I just wanted to show this because this makes it very clear that all three of these surveys and there is a two different types of measurements for each as C so that's why we have these two rows lipid it's still kind of interesting because they're all on the left side of the Planck value but we think that it is less than 82 Sigma difference. Whether that really motivates you to look for new physics explain that, that's up to you but I think that upcoming datasets will help to reveal more about that story. Looking forward, from KiDS press' DES, the more statistical power, the more systematics we learn about. It didn't go into any of these details but one thing I want you to take away is a lot of the things that we worry about for these lensing cosmology analyzes, so we call them astrophysical systematics like intrinsic alignments which I mentioned earlier. We also care about the impact of climate down like baryonic physics. We're learning a lot about galaxy formation and evolution through JWST and previously through HST and many other surveys. There's a lot of synergy in that area I think JWST is revealing a lot about these things. I think

them interesting but from a systematics perspective and from the galaxy evolution perspective. I think that's one particularly promising synergy. The last thing I will point out here is that this work builds off of the releases of all three of these collaborations. Highly encourage you to go check out. Each of these surveys have their own webinar summarizing so you might find that useful. And then, I said I would say something about JWST week lensing so far. There's not much I am aware of but there is this one paper by Finner et al which conducted week lensing of this image. There's a lot of strong lensing results from this rereleased observation but as far as I can tell, this is the first and maybe only week lensing analysis yet. Happy to hear if people in the audience know of other ones that exist so far. There is -- as we've heard earlier in the conference, there's many more results to come with COSMOS web and I think eventually we will also be able to do week lensing and that includes week lensing not just the cosmic shear or logical structure they're talking about week lensing like this result behind massive clusters or massive groups. Even weak lensing by galaxies. Galaxy-Galaxy lensing. Sort of the last main section. I wanted to go back and talk about how we are preparing for Roman. This is telling us about the process by which we go from light coming from the distant galaxy as it propagates through the universe and it will observe it with Roman and then we won't have to deal with the atmosphere but other surveys do like Rubin Observatory and observe the telescope optics. Before Hubble. Finally, will receive the light on detectors and we want to receive this right. We will receive the light. Actually, we are calibrating our point spread function typically on bright stars. But we do is try to model how different this image is from what we would expect the stars to look like in order to calibrate the shape measurement of galaxies. And then, I'm going to very briefly talk about some efforts that happened in the detectors. There is quantum yield to maturity diffusion, brighter-factor effect. These are effects that can cause some sort of effect on the images and then I will not talk about these parties are also super interesting detector effects which we will need to account for in the future. These are some aspects of nonlinearity which also contribute that we do need to include in our models. I'll talk a little bit about the important ones in the next slide. So, we need to know our point spread function for Roman really, really well. We need to know it within less than 0.1% in terms of the shape and size. Then, as I said, because these models are typically based on measurements of stars, we need to characterize and understand all of the detector effects and also telescope effects. Many efforts that build up here. The exciting thing is that we have all of the 18 detectors installed in the focal plane and there's a lot of test data that already exists from detector characterization lab at Goddard and there is also more WFI that will be available in a few months. The nondestructive read capability of these IR detectors enables correlation function is not just as a function of spatial position, but also as a function of time. We can use that to understand nonlinearities. Just wanted to give a quick shout out to my collaborators. And there is also invaluable contributions from the GCL at Goddard and product collaborators in our previous science investigation team. So, brighter-fatter effect is happening because of as the electrons build up in a pixel is, their self propulsion so it's more likely that an incoming photon if it's already coming into a world that is very full of other electrons were kind of be repulsed out to the nearby neighborhood. And then enter pixel capacitance is a cross of torque which is described as a parasitic capacitance because they are all connected to the readout. Kind of direct -- they're all kind of listening to either their nearest neighbors in terms of the signal. I'm a big four times skip over classical nonlinearity but that's pretty standard. There's a bunch of papers that you can

look at for more information. Then, we've been making maps based on our correlation function analysis of some of the detector effects. This bottom Pro is the church diffusion which is modeled as a Gaussian so these are covariance matrix elements. The top panel describes the quantum yield. I'll skip through this but it's just to say that we are making maps and I should say at least with these axes are. These are exposition and why position where we have divided up out for KX forget detectors into groups of Dutch groupings of 128X128 pixels. This can be used as inputs to emit simulations. To make some sort of realistic idea of what the actual galaxies will look like and allow us to test things like shape measurement algorithms, just different strategies for observations, different strategies, and a lot more. This is the an example here from the image simulation where does bring up a group of galaxies were in Rubin Observatory, this would show up as branded galaxies but the basis for this is also the same as used for some recent Rubin Observatory dark matter simulations. We can do this comparison between how Rubin would see it and how government would see it. Just some thoughts on synergies with JWST and prevented with adding Roman will benefit a lot from lessons learned from JWST detector test data and also the sky calibration and everything that we and everything we are learning from the, yeah, previously the commissioning and the odd sky data which is helping us develop our understanding of the JWST and mentioned earlier, revolutionizing our understanding of galaxy information and that will help us also understand systematics in some sense. There is lots of future cost correlations and overlapping fields so one thing is galaxy lensing where a selection of objects in JWST but we are actually mentioning Mike measuring the lensing so this has to be overlapping fields but you can actually think about JWST or HST snapshots and make sure you have Roman cover the wider area. I think that's quite exciting. To say for this plot that this you showing other similar time experience going on, Rubin, Euclid, all complementary. All right. Yeah, maybe I will just skip here to my overall summary. I've run out of time. But, yeah, we've been doing a lot of work mostly from ground-based surveys and so currently we are at a 2% position on this product. Currently it doesn't seem to be particularly inconsistent, but we are excited about the upcoming results from JWST and then finally will be using a lot of the detector test data to understand the systematics ahead. I am really excited about what is to come. Thank you.

Okay, we have time for just one or two questions. Can I have the next speaker, we will get you set up. Any questions online? Okay, I'm curious if there is any particular parts that you care more than others? Do you care about the core than the diffraction spikes? Or do you just need the whole thing to be characterized to less than .1%. Ami: I guess we need the whole thing to be characterized for things like diffraction spikes. I mean, we can probably avoid using stars that have diffraction spikes for measuring for modeling the PSF or be able to model the diffraction spikes well enough to, yeah, be focusing on the core of the PSF. But it is important to actually know, yeah, I will ask about it. Okay. Yeah, thank you for the wonderful talk. I'm curious about your last slides you're skipping. I see some other places where we can concentrate in. Some dark energy related tensions. Can you say more about how we can solve these problems? Ami: What was the last part? I know that there are some tensions when comparing the results and some other measurements. Or maybe there is not. I mean, I wonder more information. Ami: Sure, yeah, so, these clouds are now in the parameter space of dark energy. So it's the equation that's relating the density to the pressure, dark energy is a question that's not fluid so if

there is no revolution, then we just have to step into that beard and place constrain on the redshift evolution of it. I'm actually not aware of any NW space tension and I think it's only in particularly the large-scale structure space. So, yeah, I don't have any particular words for that, although, I do know I'd say like really dark energy is a common theory which we have said will help to resolve these types of tensions, that might be something to stay tuned to. But, yeah, the important thing here is the different types of observations going into the cloud on the left. So I've really only been talking about weak lensing, but I did mention galaxy clustering. Weak lensing of galaxy lensing, cosmic shear, clustering, the three by two and then you can think about adding all the large scale cluster Robespierre that that should give us different types of systematics and cancel out -- not cancel out, but a different view which you know, they hopefully do not have all the systems in common. We should really be getting a better understanding. Yeah. Okay, let's think Ami Choi again. If you have any other questions, let's take them to slack.

Jongwon Park: Population III protostar variability in an elliptical orbit

Our next speaker is Jongwon Park. you'll be talking about Population III Protostar variability. Now, Jongwon Park is going to start us off. Jongwon: Like this? Okay. Thanks for giving me a chance to be able to talk here. My name is Jongwon Park, I'm a PhD student at the University of Maryland. I'm working and collaborating with Hokkaido University. Today I'm going to talk about the future that might be seen by the JWST and Roman Space Telescope. So, what is a Population III star? Population III stars are a metal free or extremely metal-poor stars and they were present in the early universe. And because of their large existence. Why should you study Population III stars? They are critical in many aspects such as the formation of the galaxy, black holes, and supernovas. First they played crucial roles in the formation of the first galaxies. So they produce heavy elements that are needed for the formation of the second generation stars and first generation stars like here. The formation of the second generation stars are regulated by the radiative feedback and explosion of stars. And Population III stars are massive. They may leave massive stellar massive black holes. At the same time, gravitational wave detections, radiation detected, the radiations were made by partial black holes with masses. This implies that the gravitation waves might have have origins like Population III stars. Finally, some Population III stars may explode as peer instability supernovas. And these explosions can be detected by JWST, and even at higher radiations. If so Population III stars are important. To study Population III stars, we perform high resolution computer simulations. We make use of hydrodynamics and develop new physics. I'm not going to expand on the technical details here. And with our simulations, we have found that the formation of Population III binaries is common. This figure shows the gas density of one of our simulations. If you look at the way there are two binaries rotating each other. A hierarchy of binaries of binaries. It represents the single particle is a single Population III star. Actually, it can be a close binary if the separation is smaller than the resolution. Similar to Population III stars. The left and right panels show the individual binaries more clearly. And we found that the Population III binaries have extension orbits. This is the most extreme case in our simulations. In this case, the medium separation is around 1,000 AU and the massive separation is about ten times larger and eccentricities about 10.8. More eccentric than this. And one thing you have to memorize is Protostar's have surfaces like this. And this extension orbits makes really interesting feature population binaries. So you remember

the Protostar's. In simulation, and circumstances like this get close to each other, there's a tighter orbit. Gas boosted. And according to the model we used, in our simulation, and 2010, this massive stars become giant stars. It means that the stars get bloated periodically and the eccentric orbit at each pericenter. If the star is bloated, they cool down, they become painted UV but they become bright and the optical. This move shows what happens in the simulation, so there are two stars where they get close, tighter infraction, and stars get bloated and radiate field shut down. And they get further away. So you can look at it one more time. There are two stars, two stars, two stars get bloated, they cool down. And they become faint in UV. So, this figure shows the accretion rate of two stars red and green, and the total in black and the separation between stars as a function of time. When two stars and circumstances like this are far away, please here at the epicenter, two stars, two Protostar's. Smaller inside due to the lower accretion rate, but when they get close to each other, when they get close to each other, the pericenter the stars get bloated, they are faint in UV, and UV photos the ionization, hit the gas, the photons drop. This might happen periodically in the binary. And here, we converted the luminosity, two JWST magnet use. The top panels represent and shows the dash it traces the rest of frame UV. Write you via, magnitude as a portion of time, and the bottom represents the rest frame optical as a function of time. And at the pericenter, if you look at the circle, at the ellipse, it becomes faint in UV. But this star becomes bright in the optical. And here, we assume the binary stars at six. In the peak brightness, the magnitude in the optical band is around 34 or 35. And one thing that's really interesting is that if you are able to see the binary stars, then what we actually see is the light from the photosphere of the stars, such as helium to emission I. And of course, stars are too faint to be seen directly, but if the binary is magnified, if the lights magnified by the foreground. Arundel on the right-hand side. It is magnified, then it will be over the levitation limit. And we are also -- we are also working on working with cosmological simulations to estimate the number of Population III stars and the detection rate of PISNe. So, we are still coding and hopefully we can present this new result soon. So here's the summary. So, two studies, Population III stars, we performed high resolution computer simulations and found that the formation of eccentric Population III stars is common. And in the extension of orbit, the stars have showed variability, so they get bloated and they become bright in the optical pure article in the epicenter. And this light is magnified by lensing and we might be able to see the variability. That's it. Thank you for listening. Okay, questions. I actually did have a question but it is gone. Left my brain. We'll ask you on Slack. Any other questions, though? Well, let's thank the speaker again. Jongwon: Thank you.

Intae Jung: Prospects on Mapping Ionized Bubbles and Tracing the Global Evolution of the Ionized Structures during the Epoch of Reionization with Roman Space Telescope

And the next speaker can come forward. Okay, our next speaker is Intae Jung who is going to give us a talk about the prospects of mapping ionized bubbles during the FSOC of re-ionization. Intae: Hello, everyone, my name is Intae Jung, I'm a postdoc here. I like to think the organized committee and for everyone to make the conference so exciting. I'm glad to be a part of it. And today I'm going to talk about the re-ionization of structures during the Epoch. So, the strongest omission line in the higher universe and its very sensitive so it can be used as a provost to increase hydrogen in the inter-galaxy medium. Here I brought a figure from the paper from 2022

which shows a compilation of a constraint on the infraction. In particular you can see the area of attention in the measurement of re-ionization. Why do we see re-ionization from the measurements? It's because it's homogenous. Here on the top three panel showing, so there are multi-observation findings for clusters coming from the UV luminous galaxies. So that suggests the re-ionization process earlier enhancing the visibility from the galaxy. This phenomena is also predicted by the multiple theoretical work so you can see here, the transformation of alpha with luminous galaxies. And we tried to see such observations that we combined almost 300 galaxies that include the addition to observations. But we measured Ly α as a function of given magnitude at over six. It's a measurement from our study. The black symbols are the measurements after the re-ionization. It's decreasing with increasing UV luminosity without attenuation, but into the organization that modulates showing the upturn trend from the UV light galaxy. The relative ratio, after re-ionization, tells us the relative transformation of Ly α . What we have is the boosted IDM transmission of Ly α from UV right to galaxies. Simplified view you can see here, what we are seeing is the enhanced Ly α visibility of bright galaxies that are likely to be located in the middle of the large bubbles so that allows the easier Ly α . So, now we are studying the I GM using Ly α . Why does it matter? The evolution of the re-ionization imprinted in the re-ionization topology. Simulation results of history to the attenuation at the bottom, if that is the case, the re-ionization is allowed by the faint galaxies. All the re-ionization and right are similar, or with bright galaxies you'd expect to see the re-ionization happen more late and a patch here. So studying the re-ionization topology allows us to study the history of the re-ionization and also the source of the re-ionization, those are the galaxies. So, before JWST, it was limited to the study of Ly α because finding Ly α is limited due to the access. It's heavily hindered by the numerous alliance but now with JWST, it's fantastic. We see Lyman-a from 10.6 galaxies and also we see extremely high systems from a standpoint from these galaxies. And one of the luminous Lyman-a, it averaged out to 8.7. With JWST we all have the access on the ultra spectrum. They were undoable before JWST. If so, it's a very exciting era, and within the fierce collaboration, I left details of the Lyman-a parameters detected in observation. So, I analyzed the target which included three Lyman-a. 52 Max .7 and 12 are luminous. So likely to be a defense for an object. Yeah, so, we have a pretty good spectrum for one galaxy and the medium grading spectrum for the latter two targets. If by analyzing the properties, we find the Lyman-a parameters are relatively metal-poor, and also have some high ionization ISM conditions. So that's very interesting. Regarding the Lyman-a, we compare the properties between measured in the JWST spec obtained from Mosfire. That's because we are seeing the different spatial reason around the two observations. from the observation, we find that the spatially extended Ly α compared to the non. It showing the distance of extended Ly α and also seeing deciding 10.6B6. Lastly, what we did is we estimate the size growth of the bubble around the parameters. And in panel, we are showing it represents the case to allow capable Lyman-a. However, these are based on the properties obtained from JWST. So, the main message and the main conclusion from the analysis, in general we need additional sources to create such a large bubble, or if that is the case, one of the luminous skeletons, if the galaxy has extremely high fraction continues that is suggested by properties. It might be able to create its own bubble without the support of neighboring sources. This is very exciting results. Yeah. They cannot be done without JWST. So multiple other studies doing the detailed study on Ly α . And so first, the JWST kept finding the galaxy of Lyman-a and different fields of

modulations. Not just about the findings, but there are multiple studies doing detailed analysis. These works are predicting the size across bubbles depending on what the measurements of the fraction. In analyzing the local density around the system. And also, detailed analysis can be possible and one of my latest work found that the Lyman-a transmission from faint galaxies, particularly when they're located in the backside of the global because in the line of sight direction are cleared out by the foreground of UV galaxies. That's very exciting results as well and there are another interesting studies coming out which shows the episodic increase of Lyman-a as well as galaxy interaction. And so now we live in a very exciting era and we can study Lyman-a. In a consistent way. We can estimate the size growth of Lyman-a based on JWST and put a constraint on the infraction based on Lyman-a observation. But then we still need more observance, that's the reason why I'm talking about here. This figure is taken from the asteroid 2020 white paper. We tried to condense why we need a larger field of view with GM to GMT to study re-ionization. I use the same analogy with Roman. You can see here, JWST is too tiny to cover the complete spectrum. Beyond the homogenous structures. Oh. Oh, yeah. So, yeah, now we see here the Roman it can cover large assimilation. So with a wide field of spectrum, the minus 17 with roughly 100 hours of exposure that is comparable to the Lyman-a detected from the luminous galaxies in previous observations. Roughly and conservatively, we can expect more than 50 luminous LAEs and one field of view. So this is a very rough estimate based on the nonLyman-a system given JWST. I'm very benefited from having speakers in the morning that proved and discussed why this telescopic is powerful to find the system and after me who can discuss a more detail explanation on Lyman-a and the capability of Roman to detect this Lyman-a system during proper re-ionization. So here, I can leave my summary and Lyman-a, probes ionized bubbles during the Epoch every annihilation. Allowing to study a whole bunch of details. So in time, you can do a self consistent -- we can study re-ionization in a self consistent way as I mentioned, and but still we need larger field of view and Roman has the capability. You know, that's the way we can go. And with Roman, we can collect very nice collection of the Lyman-a targets and after this, we can do the follow-up observations to do a much more detailed study. So this is the end of my presentation. And I will take your questions. Thank you.

Questions? I have a question if nobody does. So, this was very exciting. In my question isn't that far off, Jenny Greene reminded us before all of the red dots that we see between four and seven and I'm wondering where where the red dots earlier times and could they leave one of the emergent Lyman-a galaxies? Intae: That's a very interesting question. I haven't thought about it. Yeah. I don't know if the numbers would match. Intae: Yeah. I mean, yeah. Thinking about this, yeah, we can multiple cases. That's a way to go. Okay, let's thank the speaker again.

Isak Wold: Lyman-alpha at Cosmic Dawn with the LAGER survey and the Roman Space Telescope

Okay, our next speaker is Isak Wold studying Lyman-a cosmic dot. Okay, thanks for having me, I'm going to be talking about Lyman-a omission, so thank you, for introducing the atomic and I'll be talking about the narrowband survey looking for Lyman-alpha omission approximating at 7. The 4-meter telescope in Chile and then I'll be focusing the majority of my talk on the Roman

Space Telescope populations with near infrared capabilities. Since they already introduced this, let me briefly go over this, with probes of the re-ionization epoch -- what we would like to do is have samples of Lyman-alpha emitters and as we probe into this redshift regime, we expect a rapid decline in the Ly α number density. But initially with the LAGER survey is looking at a rapid decline, Lyman-alpha makes it very sensitive to the ionization state. Here is my one slide I'm trying to summarize. At its conclusion, it makes use of dark energy cameras in the near infrared as well as custom-made filters with a central wavelength and our latest, based on the evolution of the number densities places constraints on the neutral hydrogen fraction. With this upper limit constraints from the LAGER survey. This is the halfway point based on the neutral hydrogen fraction which is a percentage of 33% or less. In addition to our own observations, I'm showing different observations from the literature. These differentiated regions show the parameter space, allowed by the plus or minus results from the literature. We find our result is in general agreement. I'm also showing here some of the re-ionization models, some of the more extreme models. As you can see here, our results pointedly favor the scenario that the re-ionization suggested in 2019. Within this simulation, you have numerous low mass galaxies resulting in an early onset and gradual transition from fully neutral to fully ionized. This re-ionization scenario, resulting in a relatively late and rapid transition from fully neutral to fully ionized. This is the halfway point of the LAGER survey. The submission of the survey will place even stronger constraints with numbers at 6.9. We want to do these number density tests outside of redshifts. They have about the biggest difference with a redshift of 8. Due to the increasing night sky background, this is where we would really like to have a space telescope with a light field of view and near infrared capability. This is where the Nancy Grace Roman Space Telescope can play a major role. We know it has a very wide field of view. Going from 1 micron to about 7. We can see above Earth's skylines and track the earth redshift coverage with Ly α emitters. And a 70-hour grism survey can reach mine depths comparable to the deepest ground base of 7. Here are these scopes of the grism simulations. They do not capture all of the field of views but key characteristics that will allow us to model all of the structural overlaps. We are starting off from an actual observation of the COSMOS field. And then objects within the field of view, we have some spectral constraints, allowing us to simulate both direct and grism images. I'm showing two grism images and we are assuming any field will have multiple position angles so we can use this additional information for multiple position angles to help distance and angle all of the overlapping spectra. I'm just showing the setups for the survey we were simulating. It has a tool with 25 position angles, giving us a total exposure time of about 70 hours. We are assuming a background level of .8 per second pixel. These findings are based on simulating all sources brighter than 25.5AB. We are simulating not only the science order but the spectra. We have line sources and simulated Lyman-alpha emitters that we were interested in trying to recover. Given this realistic galactic field, we are going to employ a reduction strategy to look for these Lyman-alpha emitters which takes advantage of all of the different position angles that a deep field may have. Our simulations have 25 different position/angles. I'm highlighting three sources, three relatively bright sources that you can see indisposition angle. The red and green sources overlap. The position angle at, the same type could occur once we use this additional information to disentangle what's going on. The reduction strategy we were using was previously employed -- it takes all of these different position angles and forms data. To look further into this, on the left, I'm showing a direct image. Multiple objects within the scales of

view. From 1.27 to 1.28. And the object circled in red has a wavelength of 1.277 microns. As I said before, this is a reduction strategy that has been employed previously out of GALEX data. It is a blind search for -- once we have the final data cube in hand, we characterize our ability to recover Lyman-alpha emitters with redshift and flux. The X axis has changed the luminosity. The flux completeness falls off at a redshift of 7.5. This is just due to the grism response function, which starts to fall off at about a micron. If we instead look at the function of line luminosity, you can see there is a reduced cosmological change that partly makes up for the grism response function, allowing us to take Lyman-alpha emitters with a Ly α luminosity of 10.43 or greater. It gives us hope that we can use a Roman grism deep field to find the density of Lyman-alpha emitters. What I would like to point out, Lyman-alpha emitters with this redshift and at this luminosity do exist. But these current surveys are either preselected based on their continuum are over relatively small volume. We really need the volume that we can obtain with Roman to constrain how their numbers are evolving. I would like to highlight the subject here. This was discovered within the HST grism survey. With other Hubble-driven surveys, it really pioneered the grism surveys with Hubble. Up until recently, this was the highest redshift Lyman-alpha emitter known. 8.7. It's a very luminous Lyman-alpha emitter. We would expect to detect an object like this within our simulations. This was also shown a few times, changing on a weekly basis it feels like with James Webb but this is the current highest Lyman-alpha redshift at 10.6. What's really interesting about this, to me, is if you look at the re-ionization models, most of them get almost 100% neutral hydrogen at redshift but we are finding Lyman-alpha emission, it'll be very interesting to see what we discover when we look for Lyman-alpha emissions with such a large volume that Roman can provide. Here is my summary. I will stop here and take any questions.

Question. This is so far from what I'm thinking about, I can't generate a question on the fly. But Andreea can. Maybe. This morning, there is the very compelling argument for the need for both getting rid of contaminants and looking at structures. Have you done any trace studies and what can you tell us about multiple? Isak: Are reduction strategy assumes we have a position angle with the data set to draw from. We have looked at -- given our reduction strategy -- how many position angles we can get away with. I think we had 15 for this specific type. We are a huge proponent of her position angles to disentangle overlapping spectra. We will have the next speaker come up as we answer the last question. Thank you for the talk. I'm not sure if I understand correctly but we were able to draw some line sensitivity from the observing strategy from your test. Is that comparable to what you listed on Romans web site? Isak: Yeah. We looked at that. What we are doing is going above and beyond the exposure time calculator. We are throwing in all of this for ground contamination. It gives us a higher background. If you take into account the background and the way with which we are reducing the data, forming this data cube, back of the envelope, we are comparable. There's not a lot of procedure we are doing here. Let's thank our speaker, one last time.

Harry Ferguson: Roman data processing, lessons learned from JWST

Our last talk, it will be given by Harry Ferguson. Harry: Thanks to the other speakers and other organizers in this conference. It has been quite enlightening. And invigorating. I will talk mostly

about data and in fairly general ways. This picture at the top is a piece of the CEERS, on the same scale is the Roman field of view. We get a huge amount of data very quickly. We need to think about that. It's nice to have a test submission in orbit. Very similar, the pipeline that we are developing here at the Institute is based on the JWST pipeline. We should be aware that many are not in there will be some people coming on so knowledge transfer is not automatic. In my collaborations and things like that. The 90-day limit of Slack is becoming a very big impediment for our knowledge transfer. [Laughs] JWST, a few highlights from my own personal thoughts on what worked well, challenges, processing NIRCcam data. I've been doing deep, high latitude observations since 1995. And a lot of them, cross science. Optimized, not just for one science objective but for multiple. Very much in the spirit of Roman. Public data and trying to cover area and depth. I've had various roles with JWST, serving as the deputy project scientist, the instrument team lead, and data analysis tools branch lead. I haven't been in a functional role with JWST for a few years. I'm coming at it as a user, almost as an external user. I'm now in a function role with Roman. Just a brief summary, we have a pipeline that has different levels, going from formatted data at level 1 to just doing the instrument signature removal, basic calibrations on individual images, and combining them into rectified images. The level that most people would like to deal with. But not everybody, of course. and level 4 for Roman, and then there is the level 2 flow. The calibration of things. What worked well? Next slide. I was reminded of a wonderful book by Norman Augustine, an undersecretary in the army but also the CEO of Lockheed Martin. Responsible for a lot of space/astronomy missions. He wrote this book based on his many decades of experience in the military-industrial complex, of building large, expensive things. He has a bunch of data analysis of how development works in practice. And then these laws he derives from them. One, it's extremely expensive to develop a high level of reliability. Increasing cost usually results in a factor of decrease in liability. 90% of the time, things go worse than you expect in the other 10% of the time, had no right to expect so much. Many of us involved in JWST had -- our expectations were that something would go wrong. [Laughs] For something so complex, it was unlikely that things would go swimmingly. That's the HST image, early release. In the JWST image, the first images were just stunning, the first data analysis from those were just stunning. The mission completed on schedule, the data release was essentially on schedule, the archive opens. We had spectra of high-res galaxies in these early observations for people interested in this kind of era. That's what we were promised for JWST and we are seeing it on the first day of the science release. The timeline, the E.R. oh observations were promised from June 3rd to July 10th, they were up and running, the July 12th ERO observations were were released. And the data became available taken before the archive was open to the public. It became available on July 12th. Papers from independent groups appeared on the archive within a couple weeks. What worked? The huge investment with engineering from NASA. While it wasn't preordained that that would work, it did work and resulted in an observatory that worked flawlessly. Lots of testing prelaunch, it helped a little bit with launch delays, testing the archiving pipelines and things like that so those could work reliably. Data formats and interfaces. That's why you do the end-to-end testing. You don't want to do that when you're in orbit and trying to retain science. The public data after commissioning was extremely beneficial to science and the observatory. I think the modular pipeline architecture was useful. I'm probably too close to it to know how useful it was. Having written pipeline modules as a user, found it pretty easy to do that. For preparation, I think it helped,

again, a little bit with the launch delay. But they were in place since 2002. People have been thinking about this for a long, long time. They have a lot of expertise. The early release science teams have been there since 2018. A bit complex for the user but certainly beneficial. There were and are challenges. There are various NIRCcam processing issues that are sort of ongoing but got us from day one. A bias drift in detectors that result in pattern noise, we have mitigation strategies but we don't have removal strategies. Cosmic-ray snowball artifacts, scattered light, cosmic-ray snowball artifacts, scattered light. The current approach that we are using with CEERS is to fit lines with those sources, there are definitely better approaches, treating it as a 1-D time series. The snowballs are big cosmic ray events, they have enough low level in the outskirts that you see these doughnut holes. Several people in the community had very rapidly developed ways to mask this a little better with the Institute pipeline. And then developing a routine to do that, but artifact removal -- one thing that isn't yet treated in any pipeline, it snowballs if they are bright enough, they are persistent. Here's the next desert. The persistence is the same place on the detector. Here's the next dither. An emission line source before we probed back to find it in the original data. That kind of thing, that subtle persistence can be something to worry about. There's less subtle persistence that we had with CEERS observations of Jupiter, happening right before that hit us. Those are pretty obvious. Scattered light is also pretty obvious with some data and results in this wisp-like feature. Somewhat successful but not completely successful in removing it. That's a major source of background fluctuation. We don't yet have a good solution for beating down and after that, you are left with various levels of background with quite a lot of spectra in it. I spent way too much time coming up with algorithms. Other approaches work but they over subtract the wings of large galaxies. Essentially, if you say okay, I'm going to use a blocked average or blocked sum image on what the fluctuations would be if it were in white noise, this is what you see. Because this guy background is fluctuating. Before background removal. And then the background removal beats this down so you are hitting the right noise. And basically, by choice, on CEERS, we beat it down to be flat scales larger than 1.5 arcseconds. Flat fields are still a work in progress. For the NGDEEP program, we aren't reaching the depths we had hoped. But the ones that were available a few months ago were definitely not good enough. We made a whole set of sky flats from all of the available data. Things have improved a lot running out of time here. A quick tale of two galaxies that reveal some of the early things, talking about the first two weeks of science release, interesting redshifts, a couple weeks later, our team realized a registration of some of the images was not perfect. The redshift then came down to around 11.5. This, several teams had different redshift distributions with different peaks. Spectra for both images, right next to each other in the sky, redshift 16 comes out at 4.9. And then the one that was 11.5, just about spot on. Spectra are great but early reduction challenges meant that a lot of papers that were put out there had very tentative results. Things that could have gone better. Communication. Between the Institute in the community, in both directions, asking questions at the community wants to ask. Who is the expert and who should I talk to if I want to dig into this? That's very difficult to find. Help desk is the starting point but that doesn't get you somebody necessarily that knows -- instantly knows the answer. What is the schedule for doing things? We've been not as good as we should be republishing the schedules of when we were planning to do something. Users didn't typically know if there is a bug in the pipeline that they should report -- there was the impediment of reporting things. On the other hand, how can software developers fix

something? There was a communication gap there. It's sometimes hard to know what is being done and when to set priorities and so on. Within the community, teams in general are really only sharing some expertise and code. There's no central discussion forum, attempts to do that haven't really gone anywhere. Some level, the biggest problem is communication, it has been borne out, the illusion that it has taken place. The simulation. Of the software and expertise on simulations for James Webb were on the instrument development teams. They had no formal responsibilities for delivering simulators. They did have some responsibilities for simulated data but the timing was problematic for software development, for the pipeline. Some of that simulation software is still proprietary. There was very little simulated data available to guide software development. That was always a struggle. Pipeline architecture, I think, right now, it takes a supercomputer to reduce CEERS. CEERS data volume was 1.2 giga pixels for the co-adds. Similar to the filters on the Roman for of view. And more on the iteration .5 giga pixels, some of those tasks were massively parallel. So that wall-clock time, there is some level of parallelization. Some memory-hungry steps, taking a 500 gigabytes of memory, tricky for users to figure out to tweak this, some overlays are still not have rolled around, there is no really easy way to drill down to the individual images who can do it. But it's not something that is simple to sort of do on the fly. And I think there is at least, from what I have seen at conferences, still a lot of community trying to figure out what to do with PSFs and there could be more centralization there. Quick recommendations, I'm sure everyone here can have their own recommendations. Adopt the good bits of community engagement, webinar kinds of things. The signs platform for Roman will have adapted to get people on there, early training and usage. Have something like the ERS program to get the data out quickly. I think it would be very useful to have a more formal lessons learned session between Roman and James Webb, including the instrument to them suffer developments, data experts. Perhaps there will be a calibration workshop sometime late in the year. Maybe that's a good place to do it. I think a fair amount needs to be done to understand particularly the pipeline performance on data sets the size of Roman. And of course, address the problems and get them into the Roman pipeline. Thank you.

Questions? This is a great talk, thank you. Given all of this, what scares you the most about Roman? Henry: Two things. One, just the sheer volume of data I don't think we have yet completely got our hands around you know. First, you like to figure out really what the tall poles are and I don't that we completely completely know. Sheer volume and that volumes going to hit us on processing, but it's going to hit the whole community and how you do science. We are putting data in the cloud but we've got to get use to bringing the computer to the data. We don't completely understand that yet. And then from the core science goals require systematic treatment of systematics at a level and in order of magnitude better than what we are doing for James Webb. That's a challenge to the overall system. Those two. Thank you, Henry, the talk was really great. You're also part of Rubin, and you deal with a huge chunk of data. So, what do you think -- is there something from Rubin that can be useful for Roman. It's on a much more compressed timeline so you do think -- Henry: Yeah, I think there's a lot of synergies, particularly in the area. The data processing is different enough and the data processing pipelines different enough so there's not enough software that we can share easily. There are pieces we probably should be sharing. But one thing we should talk about is data displays across the countries. You want to look at large patches of skies. I don't think that sort of an unsolved problem. And the

other thing is, the whole ecosystem of dealing with giant data sets in the cloud, bringing computing data to the things, we are developing a system that's very similar to what Rubin is doing. We are talking to them but that level of sharing I think, hopefully will help both every organization that is making these kind of platforms. To make them useful. Okay, next question? I remember the question or the thing I was going to say at lunch or ask you about. So I've heard that during commissioning for JWST. There was some freezing of software, you know, just things keep working the way they work and wouldn't be breaking all the time. This sort of normal ecosystem these days, things break a lot of time because they're coming in from everywhere and it's a community sort of driven thing. So, how do you best insulate or protect pipelines, you know, even though they're not individual people doing it. How do you insulate from all of those effects with things breaking all the time, just slowing everything down of course? Harry: Yeah, it's a tough problem. You know, having stable releases with some kind of reasonable schedule that people can plan for. I think that is part of the approach. If the release time scale is like six months or something like that, that is too long for science. So people cannot wait that long. And so you need something in between that allows people to get fixes that they care about quickly and, yes, they'll have to deal with some level of instability because there's no way to make it perfectly stable. I think especially for Roman and JWST, with GitHub you can come up with minor or intermediate releases or something. You know, it has problems but I think it is fairly workable. Okay, one more question and I think we will have to push this want to slack but I think people have thoughts. If we want to make sure we have time for discussion. Thank you for your talk. I have a question, if I work really hard to find out which part of the pipelines or corrections, are we talking about the space telescope. I expected all year round. What are your thoughts on that? Harry: That comes back to, yes. I completely agree. It's hard and I work here. I also don't know. It's a very hard to know where the expertise is and what people are doing and what their plans are. For releasing it. And I do think we can benefit from some more openness. And I actually sort of feel like sometimes we think we are being open and talking to people but somebody who isn't in the right room or on the right mailing list or whatever doesn't know. If so, yeah, it's a communication gap, a big one.

All right, so we will close there. Can you introduce the discussion section? Thank you so much. I want to say as the chair of the -- the co-chair of the documentation effort, we have plans. For Roman, not for JWST. Thank you, everyone, and I think the last talk has set us up for a discussion session because the question of how you want to interact with the design survey is one of the topics and what your plans are for the data current from Roman is also one of the topics of discussion. So as we did on Wednesday, the topics are pasted on tables in the cafe. Please walk around and peek at the topic you want. Or verbally the topic you chose Wednesday so there some continuity, so please feel free to switch. Please choose someone who will synthesize with your group with what your group discussed and that person will give a 1-2 minute update of the summary session. Thank you.

Live captioning was provided by CaptionMax. Some formatting and light editing was included by the Local Organizing Committee for added clarity, but there was no attempt to correct all live captioning errors.

STScI | SPACE TELESCOPE
SCIENCE INSTITUTE